

Modification of Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment Method to Improve Objective Weighting Accuracy in Multi-Criteria Decision Making

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Abstract: Multi-criteria decision-making methods (MCDM) have an important role in various fields because they allow decision-makers to consider different aspects or criteria simultaneously. Weighted aggregate quantity product assessment (WASPAS) is a MCDM that combines the advantages of the weighted quantity model (WSM) and weighted product model (WPM) approaches. The challenge in ensuring the accuracy of the criteria weights using the WASPAS method lies in the sensitivity of this method to the given weight, which greatly affects the final result of the decision. Modifications are required in the WASPAS method to improve the accuracy and objectivity of weights, especially since weights have an important role in determining the final result. One approach that can be adopted is the integration of data-based methods using correlations between criteria. This modification not only improves the reliability of decision results, but also allows the WASPAS method to be more adaptive in dealing with complex and dynamic problems with interrelated criteria. The results of Pearson's correlation value from the combination of WASPAS with MEREC, ROC, and WASPAS-IC have a very strong correlation with each other. Meanwhile, Entropy had a lower correlation with other methods, but still showed a fairly good positive correlation with most methods, especially with WASPAS-IC which had a correlation of 0.947.

Keywords: accuracy; decision-making; MCDM; modification; WASPAS-IC

1. Introducing

Multi-criteria decision-making methods (MCDM) have an important role in various fields because they allow decision-makers to consider different aspects or criteria simultaneously, resulting in more comprehensive and objective solutions¹⁻³. Taking into account various interests that may conflict with each other, MCDM provides a systematic framework for achieving optimal and accountable decisions⁴. Weighted aggregated sum product assessment (WASPAS) is a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method that combines the advantages of the weighted sum model (WSM) and

weighted product model (WPM) approaches. This method provides flexibility by allowing decision-makers to adjust the weight of each criterion according to the relevant priorities^{5,6}. WASPAS calculates the combined score by integrating the sum and weighted multiplication results (product) of each alternative against the assessed criteria, resulting in a more robust and accurate approach in the evaluation process. The main advantages of WASPAS are its ability to handle different types of data, both quantitative and qualitative, as well as its sensitivity in generating more stable alternative rankings⁷⁻⁹. This method is widely used in supplier selection, project management, and performance evaluation in various

sectors due to its ease of implementation and the validity of the results produced. The main advantages of WASPAS are its ability to handle different types of data, both quantitative and qualitative, as well as its sensitivity in generating more stable alternative rankings¹⁰⁻¹²). Another advantage of the WASPAS method lies in its ability to combine two classical approaches, namely WSM and WPM, into one integrated calculation framework, thus providing more accurate and balanced results. The systematic and relatively simple calculation process makes WASPAS easy to implement, both manually and in computer-based systems. This method is also able to handle various types of criteria, both benefits and costs, and can be applied to decision-making problems with a large number of alternatives and criteria without sacrificing efficiency. This method is widely used in supplier selection, project management, and performance evaluation in various sectors due to its ease of implementation and the validity of the results produced. Improving the accuracy of objective weighting is very important because the weight of the criteria has a direct influence on the validity and reliability of decision-making results^{13,14}). Accurate weights reflect the relative importance of each criterion in the context of the problem being analyzed, resulting in more precise and accountable decisions. In many cases, the weighting done subjectively tends to be biased towards the preferences of certain individuals or groups, which can reduce the fairness and accuracy of the final result¹⁵). The use of objective methods is an urgency to ensure that weighting is based on measurable and transparent data¹⁶⁻¹⁸). Improved weighting accuracy also helps in addressing the complexity of multi-criteria issues, especially in critical sectors such as health, environment, and strategic management, where wrong decisions can have a significant impact. In addition, objective weighting accuracy provides a stronger basis for alternative evaluation, especially in situations with many competing criteria or high complexity. With objective weighting, the decision-making process becomes more transparent and acceptable to various stakeholders, because it is supported by a scientific and systematic approach. In the era of big data, accurate weighting also enables the integration of advanced analytics to process data at scale, improving the efficiency and speed of the decision-making process^{19,20}). Thus, investing in better weighting methodologies not only improves the quality of decisions, but also creates trust and legitimacy in the overall decision-making process²¹). Inaccuracies in ranking results often occur due to inflexible weighting, where the weight of the criteria is considered fixed without considering the context or dynamics of the problem at hand²²). In real-world situations, the relative importance of each criterion may change depending on certain conditions, such as changes in strategic priorities, environmental factors, or stakeholder needs²³⁻²⁵). When

weights are not adjusted for these changes, the ranking results can become less relevant and not reflect actual needs. For example, in supplier evaluation, criteria such as cost may be more important under tight budget conditions, but quality or speed of delivery becomes a priority when there is an urgent need. If the weighting is not flexible enough to capture these changes, the resulting results risk ignoring critical factors. Therefore, adaptive weighting methods that take into account the dynamics of the situation, are essential to ensure accurate and contextual ranking results²⁶).

The challenge in ensuring the accuracy of the criteria weights using conventional methods is often related to subjectivity and inconsistencies in the assessment process^{27,28}). Conventional methods, such as direct weighting or expert opinion-based methods, rely heavily on human judgment which can be influenced by personal biases, individual preferences, or a lack of a thorough understanding of the relationships between criteria²⁹⁻³¹). The challenge in ensuring the accuracy of the criteria weights using the WASPAS method lies in the sensitivity of this method to the weights given, which greatly affects the final outcome of the decision. Accurate weighting often requires in-depth analysis and reliable data, but in practice, it is often determined subjectively based on expert opinion or preliminary estimates that can be biased. Therefore, validation and re-evaluation of the weights used, as well as the possibility of integrating objective methods such as entropy analysis or data-driven techniques to improve accuracy, are required.

Modifications are needed in the WASPAS method to improve the accuracy and objectivity of weights, especially since weights have a crucial role in determining the final result. One approach that can be adopted is the integration of data-driven methods using intercriteria correlation. The modification of the WASPAS method by integrating intercriteria correlation aims to improve the accuracy and objectivity of weights by utilizing the relationship between criteria in the weighting process. Intercriteria correlation allows correlation analysis between criteria to identify redundancies or inconsistencies, so that the resulting weights better reflect the contribution of each criterion independently. In this way, the influence of criteria that have a high correlation can be adjusted so as not to dominate the decision results disproportionately. This modification not only improves the reliability of decision results, but also allows the WASPAS method to be more adaptive in dealing with complex and dynamic problems with interrelated criteria.

1.1. Related work

Various studies have focused on modifying the WASPAS method to improve accuracy, objectivity, and applicability in multi-criteria decision-making^{32,33}). The following is a study conducted in combination and modification of the

WASPAS method.

The combination of criteria importance through inter criteria correlation (CRITIC) and WASPAS is a new joint decision-making approach used to track employee time and attendance³⁴.

The integration of entropy and WASPAS as an alternative to the entropy-weighted MCDM approach proposed in this study provides a solid foundation for future applications in various decision-making contexts and research domains³⁵. The combination of methods based on the effect of elimination criteria (MEREC) and WASPAS was used with the aim of weighting in multi-objective optimization with discrete solution areas already used⁶.

The rank order centroid (ROC) approach as a weighting technique and the WASPAS approach to determine the best alternatives in the case study of internet service provider selection, resulting in a final value that reflects the extent to which each alternative meets the specified criteria³⁶.

Previous research that has been carried out by combining the weighting method in WASPAS, so that it becomes a reference in this study to modify the WASPAS method which will produce objective criteria weighting.

1.2. Research objectives

The purpose of this study is to develop a modified WASPAS method to improve the accuracy of objective weighting in multi-criteria decision-making using intercriteria correlation. This study also seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of the modification method through its application to real case studies, as well as compare its performance with conventional methods. The results of this study are expected to provide a more innovative and accurate approach in determining the weight of criteria objectively, which can ultimately improve the quality of the decision-making process.

1.3. Research contributions

The WASPAS method is a multicriteria decision-making method that combines two approaches, namely WSM and WPM. Although the WASPAS method is known as an efficient and flexible approach to multicriteria decision-making, there are several drawbacks that need to be considered. One of the main weaknesses of this method is the assumption of independence between criteria, where WASPAS considers that each criterion stands alone without any relationship or correlation with each other, as well as the subjective determination of the weight of the criteria is also a challenge in this method. The Fuzzy-WASPAS method is a development of the WASPAS method that integrates fuzzy logic to handle uncertainty and ambiguity in the alternative assessment of criteria³⁷. While this approach is more flexible in capturing the subjective preferences of decision-makers, there are some drawbacks that come with it. One of the main drawbacks

is that the determination of the scale is fuzzy and membership functions are often subjective and do not have a standard, which risks producing biased or inconsistent results if not calibrated correctly. The Grey-WASPAS method is designed to address uncertainty and incomplete data in the multicriteria decision-making process³⁸. One of the main drawbacks is the complexity of the calculation process, especially in the stage of determining the relational gray coefficient and converting the data into gray numbers which requires special adjustments and foresight in processing interval data. In addition, the interpretation of gray values is not always intuitive for decision-makers, especially if they are not familiar with gray systems theory, which can hinder understanding and belief in the final outcome. Grey-WASPAS has also not explicitly considered the correlation between the criteria, so that if there are strong interrelated criteria, the information captured can become redundant and affect the validity of the decision results.

This study made a significant contribution to the development of the WASPAS method by modifying its algorithm to improve the accuracy of objective weighting in multi-criteria decision-making. The main innovation of this study lies in the modification of intercriteria correlation into the WASPAS algorithm, which results in a fairer and more reliable criterion weighting process. In addition, this study contributes a new model that allows sensitivity analysis to changes in weights and criteria, thus providing decision-makers with deeper insights into the impact of variables on the final outcome. With the application of the modified method to real case studies, this research not only provides practical relevance for various fields, but also enriches the academic literature in the development of MCDM.

This research makes an important contribution to the development of the MCDM method through the modification of WASPAS, this modification is designed to improve accuracy in objective weighting, which is a key element in ensuring fairness and reliability of decision-making results. This research not only contributes to improving the quality of the decision-making process, but also provides a solid foundation for adaptation and innovation in other MCDM methods. The proposed modifications in WASPAS can be a reference for the development of methods that are more responsive to the needs of decision-makers in the era of increasing data complexity. The research also promotes the improvement of the efficiency and effectiveness of decision support systems by ensuring that the end result is not only based on intuition or subjectivity, but on measurable and objective analysis³⁹⁻⁴¹. In the long term, the contribution of this research is expected to facilitate the implementation of MCDM solutions in various sectors, ranging from business, government, to project management, as well as strengthen the role of the WASPAS method in the data-

driven decision-making ecosystem.

2. Methodology

2.1. WASPAS modification framework

The WASPAS modification framework focuses on developing algorithms to improve accuracy in multi-criteria decision-making. This modification integrates a new approach to criterion weighting to increase sensitivity to data dynamics. The framework is designed to address the limitations of conventional WASPAS, such as a lack of sensitivity to small changes in data or weight distribution, resulting in a more robust, objective, and efficient decision support system. Figure 1 is the stages in the WASPAS modification framework.

Fig. 1: WASPAS modification framework

The WASPAS method modification framework includes the addition of five new stages in green in each stage that aims to improve the flexibility, accuracy, and robustness of the model in multi-criteria decision-making. Modifications at this stage ensure that the new WASPAS method is better able to deal with complex data and produce more objective and reliable decisions.

2.2. WASPAS modification

The modification of the WASPAS method by considering the intercorrelation between the criteria named weighted aggregated sum product assessment correlation intercriteria (WASPAS-CI) aims to improve the accuracy of weighting and decision-making results. In this approach, the criterion weights are not only determined based on traditional subjective or objective methods but are also analyzed by calculating the correlation relationship between criteria using correlation techniques. Positive or negative correlations between criteria are used to identify redundancies or conflicts between criteria, so that the weight of the criteria can be dynamically adjusted to reduce bias or dominance of certain criteria. This modification has a direct impact on data normalization and

aggregation of WASPAS values, where the relationship between criteria affects the aggregation results in both the sum and product methods. By incorporating intercorrelation, the modified WASPAS method becomes more sensitive to the interaction between criteria, so that the final results of alternative ranking are more representative to real conditions and relevant in complex decision-making.

The stages of the WASPAS-IC method aim to improve accuracy and flexibility in multi-criteria decision-making, and be able to deal with data complexity. The WASPAS-IC method produces a more reliable, adaptive, and relevant decision-making approach in various application contexts. The explanation of each stage in WASPAS-IC is explained as follows.

Step 1: result matrix, this stage is the first step to compile alternative assessment data based on predetermined criteria. The decision matrix contains the performance values of each alternative to each criterion, which can be quantitative or qualitative data that has been converted into numbers.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{i1} & \dots & x_{in} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Step 2: normalize the criteria matrix, this stage of the values in the decision matrix is normalized to make all the criteria are on the same scale. Normalization is carried out so that criteria with different units of measurement do not dominate the final result.

$$a_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^j x_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

Step 3: rating value, the rating value for each alternative against each criterion is calculated. This value is the result of the process of adjusting the data based on a specific weight or method to reflect the relative performance of each alternative.

$$R_i = \ln \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^n |\ln(a_{ij})| \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

Step 4: the value of the elimination criteria, this stage is used to identify alternatives that do not meet certain threshold values in the elimination criteria. Alternatives whose values are below this threshold will be eliminated from further analysis.

$$R'_{ij} = \ln \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k,k \neq j} |\ln(a_{ij})| \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

Step 5: evaluate the value of the criteria, the value of each criterion is evaluated to determine its relevance to the final decision. These evaluations often involve statistical methods or weighting based on data distribution.

$$E_i = \sum |R'_{ij} - R_i| \quad (5)$$

Step 6: criterion weight, the criterion weight value is determined based on the importance of each criterion in the decision-making process. This weight reflects the relative contribution of each criterion to the final result.

$$w_j = \frac{E_i}{\sum E_i} \tag{6}$$

Step 7: normalization, the normalization process at this stage is carried out to unify the weights of the criteria so that they have a consistent scale in the range of 0 to 1. Normalization ensures that the weight of the criteria can be compared directly and accurately.

$$x_{ij}^* = \begin{cases} \frac{x_{ij}}{\max x_{ij}}; \text{ for benefit criteria} \\ \frac{\min x_{ij}}{x_{ij}}; \text{ for non benefit criteria} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Step 8: final grade, each final value for each alternative is calculated by combining the performance value of the alternative against each predetermined criterion and weight. This final score is used to rank alternatives and choose the best alternative according to the purpose of the decision.

$$Q_i = (0.5(\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^* * w_j)) + (0.5(\prod_{j=1}^n (x_{ij}^{*w_j}))) \tag{8}$$

The WASPAS-IC method by considering the intercorrelation between criteria offers a significant improvement in the accuracy and objectivity of multi-criteria decision-making. By utilizing correlation analysis, the weight of the criteria can be dynamically adjusted to reflect the relationship between the criteria, and increase relevance. The WASPAS-IC method not only improves accuracy and objectivity, but also expands its application in solving complex and dynamic decision-making problems.

3. Result and discussion

The application of the WASPAS-IC method in solving multi-criteria decision-making problems. This method was modified by considering the correlation relationship between the criteria to improve the weight accuracy and relevance of the results. This study explores how the integration of correlation analysis affects the weight of the criteria and its impact on the resulting alternative rankings. The discussion included analysis of alternative performance, the effect of modification on model sensitivity, and comparison of results with other decision-making methods. The application of the WASPAS-IC method aims to illustrate the advantages and effectiveness of the WASPAS-IC method in producing more objective and adaptive decisions on data dynamics.

3.1. Supplier selection case study

Case studies in supplier selection, companies are often faced with interrelated criteria, such as sales performance, reputation, financial capability, geographical location, and quality of customer service that require a more comprehensive approach to objectively assess the performance of each supplier. Table 1 is the performance assessment data of each supplier against the criteria used.

Table 1: Supplier performance assessment data

Name	C0A	C0B	C0C	C0D	C0E
Supplier DF	4500000	7	9	8	9
Supplier RD	3000000	6	8	7	8
Supplier AH	6000.000	8	7	9	8
Supplier GY	2000000	6	9	6	7
Supplier TR	3500000	9	6	8	7
Supplier EQ	1500000	7	8	7	9
Supplier BS	5000000	8	8	9	8

Sales Performance (C0A) is benefit: This criterion refers to the supplier's ability to consistently meet sales targets and demand volumes. Sales performance includes how effective and efficient suppliers are in selling their products or services, including the ability to respond to market demand, achieve sales targets, and maintain good relationships with customers. Assessments of sales performance can include historical data, sales trends, and the supplier's ability to meet specified delivery schedules. Reputation (C0B) is benefit: Supplier reputation refers to the image or perception that the public or customers have of their credibility, reliability, and integrity. A good reputation shows that the supplier has solid experience in providing quality products or services and fulfilling the promises given to customers. Reputation evaluation can be done by looking at customer reviews, testimonials, and industry experience that show the extent to which suppliers are respected in the market.

Financial Capability (C0C) is benefit: Financial capability refers to the financial stability and capacity of suppliers to meet their obligations in the long term. This is important to ensure that suppliers can cope with market fluctuations, make the necessary investments, and continue to operate properly. Financial capability analysis includes a review of financial statements, liquidity, debt ratios, and the ability to manage good cash flow.

Geographic Location (C0D) is non benefit: Geographic location reflects the proximity of the supplier to the company that made the selection, which can affect the cost of delivery, delivery time, and the accuracy of delivery of goods or services. Suppliers who are located closer tend to have an advantage in terms of faster delivery and lower shipping costs. This location factor is also important to minimize the risk of delays or problems in shipping goods.

Quality of Customer Service (C0E) is benefit: Quality of customer service measures how well suppliers provide after-sales support and handle customer problems or complaints. Suppliers who have good customer service tend to be more responsive, able to resolve problems quickly, and provide satisfactory solutions. Quality customer service is essential in building long-term relationships with clients and ensuring continuous customer satisfaction.

3.2. Implementation of the WASPAS-IC Method

The implementation of the WASPAS-IC method in supplier selection aims to increase accuracy and objectivity in decision-making involving various interrelated criteria. The following are the steps in the implementation of the WASPAS-IC method:

Step 1: decision matrix, this stage is the first step to compile alternative assessment data based on the criteria that have been determined from the assessment data of table 1 and created using (1).

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 4500000 & 7 & 9 & 8 & 9 \\ 3000000 & 6 & 8 & 7 & 8 \\ 6000000 & 8 & 7 & 9 & 8 \\ 2000000 & 6 & 9 & 6 & 7 \\ 3500000 & 9 & 6 & 8 & 7 \\ 1500000 & 7 & 8 & 7 & 9 \\ 5000000 & 8 & 8 & 9 & 8 \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 2: normalize the criteria matrix, at this stage the values in the decision matrix are normalized so that all criteria are on the same scale calculated using (2).

$$a_{11} = \frac{x_{11}}{\sum_{i=1}^j x_{11,17}} = \frac{4500000}{25500000} = 0.1765$$

The results of the calculation of the normalization value of the criterion matrix that has been calculated using (2) are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Normalization of the criteria matrix

Name	C0A	C0B	C0C	C0D	C0E
Supplier DF	0.1765	0.1373	0.1636	0.1481	0.1607
Supplier RD	0.1176	0.1176	0.1455	0.1296	0.1429
Supplier AH	0.2353	0.1569	0.1273	0.1667	0.1429
Supplier GY	0.0784	0.1176	0.1636	0.1111	0.1250
Supplier TR	0.1373	0.1765	0.1091	0.1481	0.1250
Supplier EQ	0.0588	0.1373	0.1455	0.1296	0.1607
Supplier BS	0.1961	0.1569	0.1455	0.1667	0.1429

Step 3: the ranking value for each alternative to each criterion will be calculated using (3).

$$R_1 = \ln \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=1}^n |\ln(a_{11,51})| \right) \right) = 1.0486$$

The results of the calculation of the ranking value for each alternative to each criterion that has been calculated using (3) are shown in table 3.

Table 3: Normalization of the criteria matrix

Name	Rating Value (R _i)
Supplier DF	1.0486
Supplier RD	1.1117
Supplier AH	1.0366
Supplier GY	1.1488
Supplier TR	1.0936
Supplier EQ	1.1390
Supplier BS	1.0401

Step 4: The elimination criterion value is used to identify alternatives that do not meet certain threshold values in the elimination criteria will be calculated using (4).

$$R'_{11} = \ln \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{5} \sum_{k,k \neq j} |\ln(a_{21,51})| \right) \right) = 0.9190$$

The results of the calculation of the value of the elimination criterion value for alternatives to each criterion that have been calculated using (4) are shown in table 4.

Table 4: Elimination criteria value for alternatives

Name	C0A	C0B	C0C	C0D	C0E
Supplier DF	0.9190	0.8987	0.9129	0.9129	0.9115
Supplier RD	0.9599	0.9599	0.9760	0.9760	0.9746
Supplier AH	0.9283	0.8958	0.8785	0.8785	0.8881
Supplier GY	0.9728	1.0030	1.0269	1.0269	1.0074
Supplier TR	0.9508	0.9701	0.9329	0.9329	0.9436
Supplier EQ	0.9388	1.0030	1.0073	1.0073	1.0145
Supplier BS	0.9177	0.8997	0.8936	0.8936	0.8921

Step 5: the value of each criterion is evaluated to determine its relevance to the final decision using (5).

$$E_1 = \sum |R'_{11,17} - R_1| = 4.8543$$

$$E_2 = \sum |R'_{21,27} - R_2| = 4.8971$$

$$E_3 = \sum |R'_{31,37} - R_3| = 4.8951$$

$$E_4 = \sum |R'_{41,47} - R_4| = 4.8951$$

$$E_5 = \sum |R'_{51,57} - R_5| = 4.8988$$

Step 6: the criterion weight value is determined based on the importance of each criterion to be calculated using (6).

$$w_1 = \frac{E_1}{\sum E_{1,5}} = \frac{4.8543}{24.4402} = 0.1986$$

$$w_2 = \frac{E_2}{\sum E_{1,5}} = \frac{4.8971}{24.4402} = 0.2004$$

$$w_3 = \frac{E_3}{\sum E_{1,5}} = \frac{4.8951}{24.4402} = 0.2003$$

$$w_4 = \frac{E_4}{\sum E_{1,5}} = \frac{4.8951}{24.4402} = 0.2003$$

$$w_5 = \frac{E_5}{\sum E_{1,5}} = \frac{4.8988}{24.4402} = 0.2004$$

Step 7: The normalization process at this stage is carried out to unify the alternative values on each criterion so that it has a consistent scale calculated using (7).

$$x_{11}^* = \frac{x_{11}}{\max x_{11,17}} = \frac{4500000}{6000000} = 0.75$$

The results of the calculation of the normalization value of the criterion matrix that has been calculated using (7) are shown in table 5.

Table 5: Normalization of the criteria matrix

Name	C0A	C0B	C0C	C0D	C0E
Supplier DF	0.7500	0.7778	1.0000	0.7500	1.0000
Supplier RD	0.5000	0.6667	0.8889	0.8571	0.8889
Supplier AH	1.0000	0.8889	0.7778	0.6667	0.8889
Supplier GY	0.3333	0.6667	1.0000	1.0000	0.7778
Supplier TR	0.5833	1.0000	0.6667	0.7500	0.7778
Supplier EQ	0.2500	0.7778	0.8889	0.8571	1.0000
Supplier BS	0.8333	0.8889	0.8889	0.6667	0.8889

Step 8: each final value for each alternative is calculated by combining the alternative performance values against each predefined criteria and weights using (8).

$$Q_1 = \left(0.5 \left(\sum_{j=1}^n x_{11,51}^* * w_{1,5} \right) \right) + \left(0.5 \left(\prod_{j=1}^n (x_{11,51}^* w_{1,5}) \right) \right)$$

$$Q_1 = (0.5(0.8557)) + (0.5(0.1696)) = 0.5127$$

The results of the final value calculation for each alternative that has been calculated using (7) are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Alternative final value

Name	Final Value (Q _i)
Supplier DF	0.5127
Supplier RD	0.4547
Supplier AH	0.5057
Supplier GY	0.4486
Supplier TR	0.4523
Supplier EQ	0.4462

Supplier BS	0.4995
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The overview of the ranking results from the WASPAS-IC method provides a more in-depth and objective insight into the selection of alternative suppliers by considering the interaction between the correlated criteria. In this process, each alternative supplier is evaluated based on predetermined criteria, such as sales performance, reputation, financial capability, geographical location, and quality of customer service. Using the WASPAS-IC approach, the weight of the criteria is adjusted based on the correlation between the identified criteria, resulting in a more representative score. The ranking results obtained reflect the most optimal supplier and in accordance with the company's needs, providing a more accurate and relevant picture in decision-making that takes into account the dynamics between the criteria shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Alternative rankings using WASPAS-IC

The graph above shows the alternative supplier rankings based on the WASPAS-IC method. Based on the final score obtained, Supplier DF was ranked first with the highest score of 0.5127. Furthermore, Supplier AH is ranked second with a value of 0.5057, followed by Supplier BS in third place with a value of 0.4995. Supplier RD occupies the fourth position with a value of 0.4547, while Supplier TR is in the fifth position with a value of 0.4523. Supplier GY is ranked sixth with a value of 0.4486, and finally, Supplier EQ ranks seventh with a value of 0.4462. This ranking reflects the performance of each supplier based on predetermined criteria.

3.3. Comparison results

The results of the criterion weight comparison are an important step in the multi-criteria decision-making process, as the weights reflect the relative importance of each criterion used. The weight of the criteria is obtained through the right method. This comparison helps decision-makers to prioritize criteria in evaluating available alternatives. With accurate weights, the results of the analysis will be more representative of the needs and objectives, thus providing a solid basis for determining the best alternative. The results of the comparison of criterion weights using the CRITIC⁽³⁴⁾, entropy⁽³⁵⁾, MEREC⁽⁶⁾, and ROC⁽³⁶⁾ methods are shown in table 7.

Table 7: Results of the comparison of criterion weights

Weight	C0A	C0B	C0C	C0D	C0E
CRITIC	0.1514	0.207	0.2765	0.1466	0.2185
Entropy	0.0455	0.1792	0.2596	0.2394	0.2763
MEREC	0.4224	0.1298	0.1801	0.1801	0.0875
ROC	0.46	0.26	0.16	0.09	0.04
WASPAS-IC	0.1986	0.2004	0.2003	0.2003	0.2004

The results of the comparison of the weight of the criteria were based on five methods of determining the weight, namely CRITIC, Entropy, MEREC, ROC, and WASPAS-IC. Each method gives different weights to each criterion, namely Sales Performance, Reputation, Financial Capability, Geographical Location, and Quality of Customer Service. The CRITIC method gives the highest weight to the Financial Ability criterion (0.2765) and the lowest to the Geographical Location (0.1466). The Entropy method shows priority on Quality of Customer Service (0.2763) and the lowest weight on Sales Performance (0.0455). In contrast, the MEREC method highlights Sales Performance (0.4224) as the most important criterion, while Customer Service Quality has the lowest weight (0.0875). The ROC method gives the highest weight to Sales Performance (0.46) and the least weight to Customer Service Quality (0.04). Finally, the WASPAS-IC method shows an almost even weight distribution, with a weight of about 0.2003–0.2004 for all criteria. These results reflect how each method has a different approach to determining the importance of each criterion. WASPAS-IC tends to give balanced weight to ensure each criterion has a relatively similar influence, while other methods highlight specific criteria based on their respective characteristics or methods.

The ranking results using the WASPAS method combined with various weighting approaches, such as CRITIC, Entropy, MEREC, ROC, and WASPAS-IC, provide diverse insights into alternative performance based on the criteria considered. The combination of the WASPAS method with CRITIC weighting prioritizes data variability and relationships between criteria, while WASPAS-Entropy emphasizes the distribution of information in the data. The WASPAS-MEREC method focuses more on the unique contribution of each criterion, while the WASPAS-ROC prioritizes criteria based on a simple order of preference. On the other hand, WASPAS-IC adopts a balanced weighting approach for all criteria. This approach allows decision-makers to understand the differences in ranking results produced by each combination of methods, so that they can choose the solution that best suits the context and objectives of the analysis. The results of the alternative ranking comparison are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Alternative ranking comparison results

The graph of the results of the comparison of supplier alternative rankings is based on five combinations of methods, namely WASPAS-CRITIC, WASPAS-Entropy, WASPAS-MEREC, WASPAS-ROC, and WASPAS-IC. Supplier DF ranks first for all methods, demonstrating consistency as the best alternative. Supplier AH has a variation in ranking, namely ranking second with the CRITIC, MEREC, ROC, and WASPAS-IC methods, but dropping to sixth place with the Entropy method. Supplier BS tends to be stable in third place for most methods, except for the Entropy method which places it in second place. Supplier RD is consistently ranked fifth across almost all methods, while Supplier TR is ranked seventh across all methods, indicating the lowest performance. Supplier GY and Supplier EQ compete in sixth and seventh place, but are more often ranked low in method combinations. This difference in ranking results reflects the sensitivity of the weighting method to the data and provides additional perspective in the decision-making process.

3.4. Discussion

Comparison of WASPAS-CRITIC, WASPAS-Entropy, WASPAS-MEREC, WASPAS-ROC, and WASPAS-IC methods is important to understand how different weighting approaches affect alternative ranking results. Each method has unique characteristics in determining the weight of the criteria, which directly impacts the priority of alternatives. WASPAS-CRITIC prioritizes data variability between criteria, while WASPAS-Entropy focuses on information distribution. On the other hand, WASPAS-MEREC highlights the unique contribution of each criterion, while WASPAS-ROC offers a simple preference order-based approach. The WASPAS-IC method, with a balanced weight distribution, provides a different perspective from other methods. This comparison not only helps to identify the most appropriate method for a particular context, but also provides insight into the sensitivity of the results to changes in weighting, thus supporting more transparent and effective decision-making.

Pearson correlation is a statistical technique used to measure the linear relationship between two variables,

with values ranging from -1 to 1. In the context of the analysis of the WASPAS-CRITIC, WASPAS-Entropy, WASPAS-MEREC, WASPAS-ROC, and WASPAS-IC methods, Pearson's correlation helps to evaluate how strong the relationship between the ranking results of these methods is. Correlation values close to 1 indicate a very strong positive relationship, while values close to -1 reflect strong negative relationships. Conversely, values close to 0 indicate the absence of a significant linear relationship. This correlation analysis provides insight into the similarities or differences in the patterns of ranking results produced by various combinations of weighting and decision-making methods, so that it can be helpful in choosing the most appropriate method for the analysis needs. Table 8 is the result of the comparison of Pearson's correlation values from the method used.

Table 8: Results of pearson correlation comparison

	CRITIC	Entropy	MEREC	ROC	WASPAS-IC
CRITIC	1	0.826	0.826		0.893
Entropy	0.826	1	0.491	0.491	0.947
MEREC	0.826	0.491	1	1	0.947
ROC	0.826	0.491	1	1	0.947
WASPAS-IC	0.893	0.625	0.947	0.947	1

Based on Pearson correlation data, the following is an explanation of the correlation between methods:

CRITIC and Entropy: A correlation value of 0.826 indicates a strong positive relationship between these two methods.

CRITIC and MEREC: The correlation of 0.826 also indicates a strong positive relationship.

CRITIC and ROC: A correlation of 0.826 indicates a strong positive relationship.

CRITIC and WASPAS-IC: A correlation of 0.893 indicates a very strong positive relationship.

Entropy and MEREC: A correlation of 0.491 indicates a moderate positive relationship.

Entropy and ROC: A correlation of 0.491 indicates a moderate positive relationship.

Entropy and WASPAS-IC: A correlation of 0.947 indicates a very strong relationship.

MEREC and ROC: Correlation 1 shows a perfect relationship between the two methods.

MEREC and WASPAS-IC: A correlation of 0.947 indicates a very strong relationship.

ROC and WASPAS-IC: A correlation of 0.947 indicates a very strong relationship.

In general, MEREC, ROC, and WASPAS-IC have very strong correlations with each other, with correlation values close to 1. Meanwhile, Entropy had a lower correlation with other methods, but still showed a fairly good positive correlation with most methods, especially with WASPAS-IC which had a correlation of 0.947.

Criterion weight sensitivity analysis is an approach used to measure the extent to which changes in criterion weights can affect the final outcome in a multicriteria decision-making process. In this study, the weight of the criteria reflects the relative importance of each criterion to the goal to be achieved. By conducting sensitivity analysis, decision-makers can understand whether alternative rating results are stable or susceptible to weight changes. If the final result remains consistent despite significant changes in the weight of the criteria, then the decision is considered robust. On the other hand, if a small change in weight causes a large change in the alternative ranking, then the decision is sensitive and needs to be reconsidered. This analysis is essential to ensure that the decisions taken are objective and reliable, especially in situations with uncertainty or differences of opinion in determining the level of importance of the criteria.

The sensitivity analysis of adding the weight of the criteria in the WASPAS-IC method is an evaluation process to assess how the impact of changes or additions of weights on one or more criteria on the final result of alternative ranking. By conducting a sensitivity analysis to weight gain, it can be known whether or not a change in a particular weight causes a significant shift in the alternative ranking. This helps in identifying the criteria that have the most influence on the outcome of the decision and evaluating the stability of the decision-making system. This analysis is important to ensure that the decisions produced by WASPAS-IC remain valid and reliable despite changes in the subjective assessment of the level of importance of the criteria. The results of alternative ranking with a scenario of 10 experiments by adding the weight of criteria of 0.05 and 0.1 to each criterion are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Ranking of criteria weight changes by increasing criteria weight

The results of this alternative ranking illustrate the change in the ranking of seven suppliers (Suppliers AH, BS, DF, TR, RD, GY, and EQ) when the weight of each criterion in the decision-making system is gradually increased. The horizontal axis indicates eleven test conditions, starting from ORIGINAL rating to Test 10 (W5+0.1), while the vertical axis indicates the ranking value, where lower values indicate a better rating. From the graph, it can be seen that the top five suppliers (AH to RD) have a very

stable and unchanged ranking in all tests. In contrast, the bottom two suppliers, namely Supplier GY and Supplier EQ, experienced fluctuations in ranking positions, especially when the weights on the W2 and W4 criteria were raised. The zig-zag pattern shown by these two suppliers shows their sensitivity to changes in the weight of the criteria, indicating that their performance is more influenced by certain factors than the other suppliers. Overall, this graph shows that the ranking system tends to be stable for most suppliers, but remains sensitive to weight changes in some cases.

The analysis of the sensitivity of the weight reduction criteria in the WASPAS-IC method is an approach used to evaluate the impact of weight reduction on one or more criteria on the final outcome of alternative ranking. Through this analysis, decision-makers can assess whether a decrease in weight on a particular criterion will lead to a significant change in the alternative ranking sequence, thus aiding in assessing the stability and reliability of decisions. If the ranking results remain stable even though the weight of certain criteria is lowered, then the decision is considered tough. On the other hand, if there is a major change, then the decision is classified as sensitive to these criteria. This analysis is important to identify the dominant criteria and ensure that the final decision is not too dependent on one particular aspect. The results of alternative ranking with a scenario of 10 experiments with a reduction in the weight of the criteria of 0.05 and 0.1, respectively, are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Ranking of criteria weight changes by decrease criteria weight

The results of this alternative ranking illustrate the change in the ranking of seven suppliers (AH, BS, DF, TR, RD, GY, EQ) at the original weight condition and ten test scenarios (Test 1 to Test 10) where the weights of each criterion were reduced by 0.05 and 0.1. From the graph, it can be seen that the top five suppliers (AH, BS, DF, TR, RD) have very stable ratings unchanged across all tests. This shows that their performance is not affected by fluctuations in the weight of the criteria. However, the bottom two suppliers, namely Supplier GY and Supplier EQ, exhibited fluctuating ranking dynamics, swapping positions between 6th and 7th positions in some test scenarios. This pattern of rating change shows that the relative performance between the two suppliers is very sensitive to adjustment of criterion weight.

From the visualization of the graph of ranking changes due to the increase and decrease in the weight of the criteria, it can be concluded that the scoring system has a high level of stability against weight variations, especially for alternatives with superior performance. The WASPAS-IC method with the weighting system and decision-making method used is quite reliable and robust. Overall, this graph highlights the importance of choosing the right weights in the decision support system, as even small changes can have an impact on the final result, especially for alternatives that are at the bottom of the standings.

4. Conclusion

The application of the WASPAS-IC method in solving multi-criteria decision-making problems. This method was modified by considering the correlation relationship between the criteria to improve the weight accuracy and relevance of the results. This study explores how the integration of correlation analysis affects the weight of the criteria and its impact on the resulting alternative rankings. The discussion included analysis of alternative performance, the effect of modification on model sensitivity, and comparison of results with other decision-making methods. The application of the WASPAS-IC method aims to illustrate the advantages and effectiveness of the WASPAS-IC method in producing more objective and adaptive decisions on data dynamics. The alternative supplier rankings based on the WASPAS-IC method. Based on the final score obtained, Supplier DF was ranked first with the highest score of 0.5127. Furthermore, Supplier AH is ranked second with a value of 0.5057, followed by Supplier BS in third place with a value of 0.4995. Supplier RD occupies the fourth position with a value of 0.4547, while Supplier TR is in the fifth position with a value of 0.4523. Supplier GY is ranked sixth with a value of 0.4486, and finally, Supplier EQ ranks seventh with a value of 0.4462. This ranking reflects the performance of each supplier based on predetermined criteria.

The results of the Pearson correlation value of the combination between WASPAS and MEREC, ROC, and WASPAS-IC have a very strong correlation with each other, with a correlation value close to 1. Meanwhile, Entropy had a lower correlation with other methods, but still showed a fairly good positive correlation with most methods, especially with WASPAS-IC which had a correlation of 0.947.

The results of the sensitivity analysis of the change in rating due to the increase and decrease in the weight of the criteria, it can be concluded that the rating system has a high level of stability to weight variations, especially for alternatives with superior performance. The WASPAS-IC method with the weighting system and decision-making method used is quite reliable and robust.

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